
A Rare Case of Retro-Sacral Epidermoid Cyst: Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Retro-sacral tumors are rare, and the majority of them are of congenital origin (epidermoid cysts, teratomas, chordomas, etc.). Among these tumors, the epidermoid cyst is the most common.

We report the case of a 38-year-old male in whom an asymptomatic mass was discovered in the retro-sacral region, and whose analysis confirmed it to be an epidermoid cyst.

The CT scan examination revealed a well-defined cystic mass in the retro-sacral space.

This work includes a discussion of the various diagnostic and therapeutic modalities, along with general recommendations.

KEYWORDS: Retro-sacral Epidermoid Cyst - Diagnosis – Treatment.

INTRODUCTION

A wide variety of rare tumors and cysts can develop in the retro-sacrococcygeal space. The majority of cases described in the literature are either isolated or reported in small series over extended periods (1-8).

These retro-sacral lesions are classified, based on their etiology and histopathology, into the following categories: congenital, inflammatory, osseous, neurogenic, and others (2,4). Among these, congenital lesions are by far the most common and include epidermoid, dermoid, and mucin-secreting cysts, as well as teratomas, teratocarcinomas, chordomas, anterior sacral meningocele, and hamartomas. This diversity reflects the histopathological variability of these lesions, related to the heterogeneity—and sometimes the controversial nature—of their organs of origin (3,5-9).

Most congenital lesions are benign cysts resulting from embryonic development, among which epidermoid cysts are the most frequent (1-13).

We report here a rare case of a retro-sacral epidermoid cyst, accompanied by a review of the literature on the different types of cysts in this region. The presentation modalities, diagnostic approaches, and recommendations for therapeutic management will also be discussed.

CASE PRESENTATION

This is a 38-year-old male, a chronic smoker and occasional alcohol consumer, with a history dating back 10 years of the gradual appearance of a mass in the sacrococcygeal region. This mass, which increased in size over time, caused discomfort while sitting, without leading to transit disturbances, local inflammatory signs, or associated neurological deficits. The progression occurred while the patient's general condition remained stable.

Upon admission, the clinical examination found a conscious patient in good general condition. Examination of the sacrococcygeal region revealed a mass localized at the level of the sacrum, measuring 10 cm in its long axis. The mass was mobile relative to the posterior plane, soft in consistency, painless, and resilient. Digital rectal examination showed a healthy anal margin, good sphincter tone, and no other abnormalities. The rest of the physical examination was unremarkable.

An ultrasound of the soft tissues was performed initially, revealing a superficial, well-defined oval formation with macrolobulated contours, hypoechoic and homogeneous, containing hyperechoic trabeculations. The measured dimensions were 66 mm × 33 mm, suggesting a benign tumor.

A pelvic CT scan was then performed, showing a well-defined subcutaneous formation at the sacral region (from S2 to S4), with an oval shape, tissue density, and no enhancement after contrast injection. This mass was in deep contact with the aponeurosis of the right gluteus maximus muscle and the median sacral crest at the level of S3. Its dimensions were 9 cm in height, 8 cm in width, and 5 cm in anteroposterior thickness.

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Images showing the presacral mass on various CT scan slices.

The patient was scheduled for surgery. During the operative exploration, a mobile mass, relative to both deep and superficial planes, measuring 8 cm in its long axis, was identified at the level of the sacrum. A complete resection of the mass, along with a biopsy of the surrounding aponeurosis, was performed.

The mass was excised en bloc, without rupture. The postoperative course was favorable, with no complications or incidents.

Images of the mass in frontal and lateral views, showing the presacral mass.

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Image showing the mass after resection

The pathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of an epidermoid cyst, with no signs of malignancy. The biopsy revealed inflammatory changes.

DISCUSSION

The retro-sacrococcygeal epidermoid cyst is a congenital or developmental cyst of ectodermal origin, which can be explained by the understanding of the embryonic development of the caudal region of the fetus.

ANATOMOPATHOLOGICAL ASPECTS:

Sacrococcygeal dermoid cysts are typically well-defined and often encapsulated. They contain serous, mucinous, or hemorrhagic substances. Occasionally, structures such as digits, fragments of intestine, or teeth are found within them. This type of cyst represents a developmental form of the caudal region, including the epidermoid cyst (containing ectodermal cells), the dermoid cyst (containing ectodermal cells and mesodermal elements), and the teratoma (containing elements from all three germ layers: ectodermal, mesodermal, and endodermal).

It is essential to check for potential invasion of the coccyx, as this sign could indicate a malignant nature. The presence of solid areas is more common in malignant teratomas (1,5,11,13,14-20). Histologically, the cyst components are mature, and the presence of immature structures suggests malignancy. The most common form is represented by a yolk sac tumor (21,22,23).

The epidermoid cyst is lined with keratinized malpighian epithelium, and its wall contains no other elements.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS:

Retro-sacral Dermoid and Epidermoid Cysts are more commonly observed in women. Although they can occur at any age, they usually manifest in adulthood, particularly between the ages of 20 and 50 (1,4-7). Most of these cysts remain asymptomatic or present with mild symptoms. They are often discovered during a routine medical examination, during pregnancy, or at the time of delivery (1,9,10,16). Symptoms primarily occur due to compression, suppuration, or rupture and fistulization of the cyst. Pressure exerted on the rectum, urethra, vagina, and pelvic nerves can lead to urinary difficulties, defecation disorders, dystocia, or partial incontinence.

About 60% of cysts may present with an abscess or fistula, either toward the skin, the rectum, or, more rarely, the vagina (19,20). In some cases, the presence of the cyst may go unnoticed, and the diagnosis is made only in the following situations (24,25,26):

1. After the onset of recurrent abscesses in the retrorectal region;
2. Following multiple surgical interventions for fistulas, without a precise origin identified at the pectinate line; in this case, the definitive diagnosis is made after histopathological examination of the abscess wall;
3. After the discovery of a protrusion, as was the case here.

RADIOLOGICAL ASPECTS:

Retro-sacral lesions can be cystic, solid, or mixed (1,2,21,22,25). They may also contain calcifications, teeth, or bone fragments, sometimes associated with bone erosions.

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Simple radiological examination of the pelvis is generally negative, although it may show a soft tissue shadow over the sacrum, calcification, or sacral bone erosion (4,11,14).

The solid and cystic components of the lesions are easily characterized by ultrasound. Fatty tissue appears hyperechoic, while calcifications and teeth produce a shadow cone. These lesions are often detected before birth during routine obstetric ultrasound (19,24-29).

CT scan allows for the determination of the size, extent, and relationships of the lesion with the sacrum, as well as its cystic and/or solid nature. Calcifications are clearly identifiable, often better than on plain radiographs. Suspected malignancy increases if there is no fat plane between the lesion and neighboring organs.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), with its sagittal and coronal sections, allows for better definition of relationships with pelvic and abdominal organs, as well as the extent of the lesion. However, MRI is not reliable for detecting calcifications (31).

Endoluminal endoscopy can be performed, but it does not provide additional information compared to other radiological modalities. To date, its use in this pathology remains limited.

In the case of a sinus or fistulous tract, fistulography may be useful to determine the location, size, and extent of the cystic lesion. Direct cytopuncture, guided by CT scan or ultrasound, allows for the retrieval of thick, viscous fluid containing keratinized squamous cells (30). Although cytopuncture is generally not necessary, it can be useful before surgery to identify possible malignant cells and differentiate the epidermoid cyst from other retro-sacral cystic lesions, such as lymphangioma, anterior sacral meningocele, mucin-secreting cyst, or pre-sacral abscess.

TREATMENT

Any retro-sacral cystic lesion should be excised upon discovery, even if asymptomatic and appearing benign. Indeed, every cyst presents a risk of malignant degeneration, estimated at 10% of cases, or may harbor malignancy, become infected, and lead to chronic complications (5,9,16,31-34).

It is essential to perform a complete dissection of all expansions and total excision of the cyst. Any incomplete excision can lead to chronic drainage from residual epithelium.

The surgical approach varies depending on the size and location of the cyst. Excision can be performed transanal, posterior trans-sacral, abdominal, or combined. Although transanal excision carries a risk of fistulization and infection, it is recommended for small lesions localized in the lower sacrococcygeal region. For larger cysts, a retroanal approach, with or without coccyx excision, is considered the safest (33).

The abdominal or combined approach is reserved for pre-sacral lesions larger than 8 cm, located in the sacral curve or with intra-abdominal extension. In such cases, the risk of rupture and dissemination of the contents is notable, predisposing to postoperative infection. Controlled aspiration of the contents can facilitate the excision of larger lesions (35,36).

CONCLUSION

Retro-sacral epidermoid cysts are benign, simple, and congenital developmental lesions, primarily occurring in women. They are typically asymptomatic, with secondary infection being the most common complication.

Malignant degeneration remains rare and is primarily observed in cases of dermoid cysts or teratomas. Complete excision, followed by a thorough histopathological examination of the entire excised specimen, confirms the diagnosis and eliminates any suspicion of malignant degeneration. Incomplete excision can lead to recurrence, as well as the formation of a sinus with persistent drainage.

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